

The Effect of Time Management and Motivation on Procrastination with Self-Efficacy as an Intervening Variable in Master's Degree Students Who Do Thesis While Working

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of time management and motivation on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working. The method used in this research is the quantitative method with incidental sampling technique. The subject of this study found 50 master's students who worked while studying in 18 hotels in the city of Semarang. The results showed a significant negative effect between time management on procrastination, then the effect had no significant effect on procrastination, individual motivation had no effect in reducing or increasing procrastination behavior in Masters or Masters level students, there was a significant effect on self-efficacy on procrastination.

Keywords: Time Management, Motivation, Procrastination, Self-Efficacy, Master's Degree Students, Thesis.

I. INTRODUCTION

A very common question asked by parents to students is "where do you want to go after graduating from college?" Of course, work is the main choice that must be achieved because that is the purpose of studying from the beginning or continuing to a higher level of education, for example, Master. Some students who have graduated from S1 have established themselves to continue studying for Masters, but not a few are suggesting to go straight into the world of work, especially in the world of work, not only highlighting degrees but also work experience. If you have an interest in continuing your master's degree while working, you usually have a strong will because doing both of these things is not easy and to avoid neglecting or procrastinating college assignments or office work, it is important to make a list of priorities to balance study time and work activities as well as rest time. However, in reality there are still many who do not realize the importance of opportunity and time efficiency in doing their daily work. This can be seen from the behavior of procrastination in completing the work that occurs in the community. Procrastination behavior leads to procrastination behavior.

According to Sugiarti, et al (2021: 3568) explaining the development of human resources needs to be prioritized as an effort to answer the challenges that arise in the era of globalization, especially related to human resources that have the potential to bring change to society. Therefore, Indonesia needs human resources with character. According to Nafeesa (2018: 56), Individuals who have poor resources will have difficulty doing things within a predetermined time limit, often experience delays, prepare things very excessively, and fail to complete tasks within the specified time limit. is said to be an individual who performs procrastination.

Based on interviews on the subject said that the subject often delays work by playing social media. Therefore, procrastination, or in other words procrastination, can be said as one of the inefficient behaviors and a tendency to not immediately start a job when facing a task. Procrastination can be seen from various aspects. This is because procrastination involves various elements of complex problems, which are interrelated with one another. Procrastination can be said simply as a delay or procrastinate starting a job. However, procrastination can also be said to be task avoidance that occurs because of feelings of displeasure towards and fear of failure in carrying out tasks. Procrastination can also be a trait of a person's habit of responding to tasks, so good time management is needed. According to Kristy (2019: 50), time management is an action that aims to obtain effective use of time to carry out certain actions that lead to goals. By implementing time management students will have self-regulation in using time effectively and efficiently, in the form of planning, scheduling, having control over, always prioritizing their interests, and not delaying work that must be completed.

Priority in time management has a big role in the success of student learning. Students who do not have an understanding of time management will be characterized by disorganized planning, unclear, inconsistent, no purpose, and lack of discipline in the use of time. Instilling an attitude of responsibility and discipline in completing tasks according to the specified schedule, will make students able to achieve learning targets by achieving optimal results (Dwi, 2016: 26). To realize priorities in time management, students must have

the motivation or encouragement to carry out learning activities to achieve the best possible results. According to Wahyudin & Margareta (2019: 81), students who have high motivation usually have thoughts, feelings, and actions that arise from within themselves that are planned and adjusted to achieve goals and do not take procrastination actions. But in practice, students tend to procrastinate and do not have a good motivation, this is revealed in interviews with students who do not have good motivation and often delay work. Students will tend to do things that will make their achievements lower or higher. However, it is possible for students who have high learning motivation but do not have good self-regulation. In behavior, for example, in making decisions, students will use feelings, therefore students who have high motivation can procrastinate doing assignments, such as doing part-time jobs that students have. Even though time and responsibilities are taken up by part-time jobs, students should not be complacent and responsible for academic activities. Thus, high college motivation is needed so that students continue to want to maintain a good level of achievement both in the workforce and in good academics, (Novita & Nugraheni, 2016: 2). Students who have part-time jobs tend to have a high desire to learn and get good grades. These things are also shown by how students enjoy their learning process and environment so that they can survive, Novita & Nugraheni, (2016: 3).

Hamidi et al, (2019: 36) individuals who have high motivation will not waste time by turning to useless things while doing tasks. Motivation is the basis for individuals to have full responsibility for the completion of music. One of the forms that individuals do is to use time effectively in completing tasks, namely by not procrastinating. On the other hand, Steel (in Hamidi et al., 2019: 36) explains that low motivation is a strong predictor of procrastination.

In addition to motivation, there is great self-confidence in the individual so that there is no procrastination in a job. Research by Rahayu & Lastary (2018: 18-19) self-confidence or often referred to as self-efficacy. With high self-confidence, it will be easy for students to complete the tasks they are responsible for. On the other hand, students who have low self-confidence will find it difficult to solve a problem and the possibility of the individual's internal quality of procrastination behavior. One of these internal qualities is low self-efficacy. As in interviews conducted by researchers that have low self-efficacy so they do not have the ability to complete tasks and do not focus on the goals to be achieved.

This is in the opinion of Pratiwi & Sawitri (in Mariskha et al 2020: 36) that the level of confidence that individuals have can encourage them to increase their ability to try to obtain information and survive in difficult situations while in certain activities. There is a negative correlation between self-efficacy and procrastination. The higher the self-efficacy, the lower the academic procrastination occurs, on the contrary, the higher the procrastination, the lower the self-efficacy. Madhuri & Mudalifah (2019: 93), Self-efficacy is a person's belief to

overcome various situations according to the goals that arise in his life with the abilities he has. That way, self-efficacy is not related to development but is related to individual self-confidence, so that the behavior of one individual will be different from other individuals.

Mariskha et al (2020: 36-37) facing the phenomenon that causes procrastination, students need confidence in their ability to face problems and take the necessary actions in completing tasks to get the expected results. The influence of self-efficacy on the individual's way of thinking will encourage encouragement and take an action to achieve a positive result for the individual himself. Self-efficacy or individual self-confidence determines effort and endurance to survive in the face of obstacles and obstacles when facing tasks.

According to Rusdi (2015: 157) in his research concluded that increasing self-confidence by trying to appear brave and full of enthusiasm in facing every activity. Students also have to fight negative thoughts and try to think positively by remembering past successes and do self-introspection by doing self-introspection on attitudes and behaviors that are always done and find out their weaknesses and strengths. Such as doing self-introduction by checking other people about themselves. As well as making plans for activities by preparing time management to be carried out and managing the time required for an activity. Then supervise and ensure the activities carried out are by the goals and plans.

Nafeesa (2018: 60) says that to avoid Time Disorganization or can be interpreted as irregular, students must manage time so that they can evaluate well how long it takes to complete the work. Another aspect of poor timing is that it is difficult for a person to decide between important and less important work to do. All work seems so important that it becomes difficult to determine what to do first. Individuals who have confusion when deciding on a job will have low self-confidence and will tend to procrastinate, whereas individuals who have high self-confidence will have high motivation in doing work.

Firdaningsih (2016: 56) self-confidence or self-efficacy theoretically is a manifestation of an individual's self-confidence about the ability to move motivation, cognitive resources, and how to act needed to successfully carry out tasks. Confidence in self-ability is very important in the task process because this factor will affect the efforts made. A person's capacity also determines an individual's level of optimism, which affects the work more so that it has an impact on the spirit of satisfying results.

According to Ansyah & Dewi (2018: 108), motivation is a psychological aspect that will affect a person's success in taking an action. Individuals will have a strong will to achieve a goal if they have achievement motivation. Individuals who have a level of self-efficacy then the individual have ease in a goal. Because these individuals have strong self-confidence,

affective aspects, motivational aspects, and good selection aspects.

The level of success in carrying out all activities to realize the goal is very much on the individual's ability to carry out the task. Students must be able to increase feelings of high self-efficacy, so that they will have confidence and trust in their abilities to keep trying even under pressure to overcome obstacles, have a strong determination, and stay focused on what they are doing by showing performance in completing academic assignments, Baron (in Rusdi, 2015: 55).

In the world of education, it can be interpreted as high learning motivation, great morale, trust from various parties, and minimal funding, time, and energy but maximum results, Daulat (in Widarto, 2017: 128). Thus, efficiency is a very urgent factor in the management of improving the quality of education, Tjipto & Kees (Widarto, 2017: 128). This is because educational institutions in general present problems that directly impact management activities.

In the world of education, the research competence of a master's degree student who is working on a thesis while working, for example, must have several things as follows. According to Sudira, et al (2015: 60), research competence and thesis writing include the ability to: formulate problems, objectives, and research benefits, formulate a framework of thought after conducting descriptions, analysis, synthesis of relevant theories and research results, reviewing the results relevant research to position the research that has been carried out, apply valid research methods, present research results, compile research results using the perspectives of various relevant theories, conclude and make further suggestions, apply format and writing according to thesis guidelines. The supporting and inhibiting factors in writing a thesis include: supporting and inhibiting factors can be classified into two, namely from within campus and outside the campus. From within the campus that hinders, for example, difficulty finding time for discussion factors with supervisors, difficulty understanding and applying research methods, difficulty analyzing data, difficulty finding references for foreign journal references, questions because course grades have not been released. The supporting factors from within the campus are as follows: Getting support from supervisors, easy administrative process, motivation to graduate, getting support from fellow classmates, a harmonious collaboration between students, getting scholarships, getting assistance in accessing foreign journal literature from other universities.

While the control from outside the campus is for example as follows: Task load at work, less able to understand foreign literature, less able to read theoretical study references, campus distance away from home, family affairs, decreased health, decreased enthusiasm for learning, difficulty in the data collection process (location). remote research), thesis development (R&D) costs. as for the things that support from outside the campus is getting family support, getting

scholarships. The most dominant supporting factors in thesis writing are lecturer support and family support. availability of competent supervisors, good academic administration services, motivated learning atmosphere, harmonious student relations, family support, availability of scholarships are positive factors to support thesis preparation.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Procrastination*

Junia & et al, (2019: 22), procrastination is the inability to use time effectively which results in a person procrastinating on work, being lazy, and not wasting time on important things. Procrastination is a specific behavior, including a. Procrastination, either to start or finish a task or activity. B. further consequences, such as delays in completion or failure of tasks; C. Involves a task that the procrastinator perceives as an important task to do, for example, an office assignment and a course assignment; D. unpleasant emotional states, such as feelings of pleasure, guilt and so on.

Savira & Widyaningsih (2021:161), procrastination is a procrastination behavior that is done intentionally on tasks. Meanwhile, Farra et al (2021: 1) explains that procrastination is a tendency to delay the completion of tasks to result in not completing tasks and even hindering their studies in higher education.

Aulia & Fidrayani (2021: 17) procrastination is an irrational tendency to delay starting or completing academic tasks to result in displeasure, and ultimately lead to failure to do what should be done.

Ramadhani & Sandya (2021:205) conclude that procrastination is a voluntary delay in tasks that must be completed by carrying out other activities that are not needed in carrying out important tasks despite knowing the impact that will arise. Individuals who have difficulty doing something within a predetermined time limit, often experience delays in preparing themselves excessively or fail to complete according to the time limit which can be said to be procrastinators.

Umah (2021: 31) procrastination is the behavior of someone who often delays time from a job or task that should be completed properly. Mostly, people have done procrastinated starting from an employee, teacher, student, and student. those who do not realize when they procrastinate. Someone without realizing will procrastinate a job or task that will make a habit and will fall into it.

Based on the description above, it can be ascertained that procrastination is an intention to cancel an important task that is carried out repeatedly so that it fails in the task or work and negative consequences such as wasting time are wasted.

➤ *Aspects of Procrastination*

The things that cause procrastination to occur in individuals, there are several aspects proposed by Solomon & Rothblum (in Aulia & Fidrayani, 2021:20), including a. Not confident, b. Anxiety, c. Perfectionist, d. Fear of failure, e. Time management, f. environment.

Almost the same thing was said by Ferrari, et al (in Aulia & Fidrayani, 2021:20) that the background of procrastination is, a. There are irrational thoughts from procrastinators, b. There is pressure in the form of anxiety about the habit of doing something that is assessed or estimated, c. Negligent and unable to manage time well, d. Held “punishment” and “reward”, e. Environment, f. Stacking of tasks. Ferrari et al (in Afriansyah, 2019: 100), say that a delayed behavior, procrastination can be manifested in certain aspects that can be measured and observed. The following aspects of procrastination are: a. Delay to start and complete tasks. b. Delay in completing assignments. c. The time gap between planned and actual performance. d. do more enjoyable activities.

Umah (2021: 31-32) individuals who often repeat procrastination are an illustration of an aspect of procrastination actors, including a. Procrastinators who prefer to procrastinate. b. There is a fear of finishing. c. Choose to do other activities. d. in making decisions. According to Rothblum (in Umah, 2021: 32), there are 3 aspects that cause procrastination, namely modifying procrastination by optimizing self-regulated learning. a. Fear of failure is a desire that experiences guilt if it cannot achieve the goal (failure); b. Averse of the task has to do with feeling unhappy with the task at hand. Excessive feelings of being burdened, dissatisfied, and disliking to carry out assigned tasks; c. The nature of depending on others and often need help, excessive in taking risks, less firm in decisions, rebellious, and difficulty in taking.

Based on the description above, it can be said that the aspects of procrastination are delaying tasks, weak time management, being late in completing tasks, doing other activities that are more fun.

➤ *Factors That Affect Procrastination*

Ghufron & Risnawita (in Nafeesa, 2018: 58-59) categorizes the factors that affect procrastination into two types, namely factors. Internal factors include physical conditions and individual psychological conditions. External Factors, a. Parenting Style, b. Environmental conditions.

Rizki (in Nafeesa, 2018: 59) suggests that the factors that affect procrastination can be categorized into three types. a. Characteristics of tasks that are perceived by students as fun or boring tasks influence students to delay completing assignments. The characteristics of boring assignments generally make students delay an assignment. b. Procrastinator personality factors, individuals who have low self-confidence or self-efficacy will be more likely to procrastinate. c. The influence of situational factors, environmental disturbances, or

distractions influences a person to delay his work. According to Mustakim (in Nafeesa, 2018: 59) the factors that can affect procrastination are: a. Locus of control is defined as the ability to compose, guide, regulate, and direct forms of behavior that can lead to positive consequences. b. Social Support Factor, is a form of encouragement carried out by the social environment in the form of verbal or nonverbal advice that provides emotional benefits or behavioral effects for individuals as social beings. c. Personality factors can be defined as a form of the traits that exist in the individual who greatly determines his behavior. Student personality will influence perception and decision making to procrastinate or not. d. Perfectionism factor, is one of the ideal self-actualizations which has 3 aspects, namely seeking neurotic majesty, demanding neurotic, and neurotic pride, or not accepting something that is not perfect. Factors Attitude and Belief in oneself (self-efficacy), a person's assessment of likes or dislikes, emotional feelings whose actions can lead to various objects or ideas. Attitudes greatly affect beliefs and vice versa, beliefs determine attitudes. About procrastination behavior, attitudes and beliefs are very influential in determining behavior. Motivation factor, as the encouragement possessed by a person to overcome obstacles in achieving, so that individuals who have high motivation show greater and more tenacious efforts.

Catrunada (in Nafeesa, 2018: 60-61), reveals about ten magnetic regions that are factors for procrastination:

- Anxiety, can be interpreted as anxiety. Anxiety eventually becomes the opposite magnetic force where tasks that are expected to be completed interact with high anxiety so that a person tends to delay the task. b. Self-depreciation can be interpreted as self-deprecation. A person has low self-esteem and is always ready to ignite himself when something goes wrong and also feels insecure to get a bright future. c. Low Discomfort Tolerance, can be interpreted as a low tolerance for discomfort. The existence of difficulties in the task at hand makes it difficult for someone to tolerate frustration and anxiety, so they turn themselves to tasks that reduce individual discomfort. d. Pleasure Seeking can be interpreted as a seeker of pleasure. A person whose seeks comfort tends not to let go of a situation that makes him comfortable. If someone has a high tendency to seek comfortable situations, then the individual will have a strong desire to have fun and have low control impulses. e. Time Disorganization, can be interpreted as the irregularity of time. Managing time means being able to estimate well how long it will take someone to complete the job. Another factor of poor time management or time management is the difficulty of individuals deciding which work is important and less important to do today. All work seems so important that it becomes difficult to determine what to do first. f. Environmental disorganization can be interpreted as a messy or disorganized environment. One of the factors of procrastination is the fact that the environment is messy or not well organized, it is probably the fault of the individual. A disorganized environment can be in the form of interruptions from other people, lack of

privacy, paper scattered everywhere, and the tools needed for the job are not available. The existence of so many distractions in the work area makes a person concentrate so that the work cannot be completed on time. G. Poor Task Approach can be interpreted as a weak approach to the task. If a person finally feels ready to work, the individual will likely put the job back because he has to start so that he is not stopped by not knowing how to start and finish the job. H. Lack of Affirmation can be interpreted as a lack of giving a firm statement. An example is a person who has difficulty saying no to a request made to him. While many things must be done because it has been done first. This can happen because they do not give honor to all the commitments and responsibilities they have. i. Hostility With Others can be interpreted as hostility towards other people. Continual anger can lead to resentment, hostility, which can lead to rejection or opposition to whatever the person says. j. Stress and Fatigue can be interpreted as a feeling of pressure and fatigue. Stress is the result of some intensity negative demands in life that are combined in the lifestyle and ability to cope with problems in the individual. The more demands and the weaker one's attitude in solving problems, and the less favorable the lifestyle, the higher one's stress. k. Internal factors include physical conditions, psychological conditions, lack of confidence, anxiety, and difficulty managing time. And external factors include parenting style, environmental conditions, task characteristics, social support, and hostility with others.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the researcher drew 3 main points that greatly influenced the procrastination factors, namely: time management, motivation, and self-efficacy.

➤ *Time Management*

According to Surur & Nadhirin, (2020: 85-86), time management is the most important thing in life, time management is related to activities, organization, activity drivers, product control, and work-related matters. Good time management is one of the important factors that can determine success. Time management is concerned with how individuals can organize or schedule each of their activities so that all work can be completed properly and on time. Things like this are often underestimated, even though implementing a good management system can increase time development opportunities.

According to Nurhidayati, (2016: 26) argues that time management is a daily process used to divide time, make schedules, to-do lists, delegate tasks, and other systems that help to use time effectively.

According to Hamiyati et al (2020:81) time management is making good use of time through careful and organized planning. Mulyani et al (2020: 101) says that time management is a person must have a target or goal to be achieved when carrying out all the work that has been planned, so that time will

be used as effectively and efficiently as possible. Good time management allows a person to work smarter, so he can complete work faster, even when under high pressure. Failure to manage time can undermine the effectiveness and cause stress.

Time Management in short can be interpreted as an art of organizing, organizing, scheduling, and budgeting one's time to produce more effective and productive work, Humes (in Rivai & Esas, 2021: 75).

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that time management can manage and use time productively, effectively, and efficiently in creating a balance between work and or other things to achieve the desired goal.

➤ *Time management aspects*

Tiger (in Nurhidayati, 2016: 26), suggests aspects of time management, namely: setting goals and priorities, time management mechanisms, control over time. According to Britton, B.K., & Tesser (in Hamiyati et al, 2020: 81) regarding the aspects that affect time management which has a scale called the "Time Management Questionnaire". Time Management Skill has 3 aspects, namely: a. Time Planning, b. Time Traps and c. Time Attitude.

Dewi (2020: 23), aspects of time management: a. Determine the schedule. b. Monitoring. c. Analysis (compare and determine effect). d. Corrective action. e. Update schedule. Aspects of time management according to Surur & Nadhirin, (2020: 86-87), Time Discipline, as explained in the notion of time management that the goal is to complete the target following the predetermined period. So it is necessary to get used to working with time discipline in other words not to procrastinate work. This undisciplined attitude makes the work increasingly piled up and not immediately resolved. Focus With What You Do, if you have made a list of tasks that must be completed, then try to always focus on work. Try to do what has been scheduled and don't be easily tempted by things that are not related to work. For example, such as playing games or often sleepy at work, things like this can delay success. Managing Long Term Time, successful entrepreneurs are people who are always busy with work and for the work is a top priority.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the aspects of time management are setting priorities, avoiding delays or delays, setting goals, controlling attitude towards time.

➤ *Motivation*

According to Sardiman A.M. (in Nurita & Kusmanto, 2016: 406), motivation is a series of efforts to provide certain conditions, so that a person wants and wants to do something, and if he doesn't like it, he will try to negate or avoid that feeling of dislike. In language, motivation comes from the word motive which means "encouragement" or stimulation or "moving

force" that exists within a person. In the Indonesian dictionary, it is defined as The causes that impel a person's actions; basic thoughts and opinions; something that is a staple. Motivation is an impulse of the will that causes a person to do an act to achieve a certain goal, Nurdin (2018: 74). According to Saptono (2016: 199), motivation is a change in energy within a person which is characterized by effective impulses and reactions to achieve goals. This definition emphasizes the physiological-psychological aspect, which explains that in motivation there are three interacting and interrelated elements, namely needs, drives, and goals. According to Syardiansah (2016: 442), that the notion of motivation is the driving force or impetus that exists within each individual and outside the individual to do something in order to achieve goals.

According to Indah (2018: 42), motivation is an impulse that arises in a person consciously or unconsciously to take any action with a specific purpose. In addition, motivation is also an effort that can cause a certain person or group of people to be moved to do something because they want to achieve the desired goal or get satisfaction with their actions. In addition, motivation can also be interpreted as an action or process that gives a reason to someone to do something. Motivation is based on the desire from within an individual. Motivation is behavior that has a goal orientation. Thus, motivation is something that creates a desire in a person, so that goal-oriented business behavior will occur, Armstrong (in Novita & Nugraheni, 2016: 2). From the three definitions of motivation, it can be concluded that the meaning of motivation, in general, is something that encourages someone to act so that business behavior is oriented towards certain goals. An intense intensity with a clear direction certainly will not delay or delay or what is called in other words procrastination is an obstacle for each individual to complete his work.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that motivation is energy, movement, encouragement in a series of efforts to achieve a goal.

➤ *Motivational aspects*

According to Saptono (2016: 201), motivation is all mental activities that are felt or experienced that provide conditions for behavior to occur. Motivation can be identified in several aspects based on its relationship to behavior, namely: a. Motivation not only stimulates a certain behavior but stimulates various behavioral tendencies that allow different responses. b. Strength and efficiency of behavior have a variable relationship with the strength of the determinant. c. Motivation directs behavior towards a specific goal. d. Positive reinforcement causes a certain behavior to tend to be repeated. e. The strength of behavior will be weakened if the consequences of the act are unpleasant.

Mc. Donald (in Syardiansah, 2016: 441-442), there are three important aspects in motivation, namely as follows: a. That motivation initiates energy changes in each individual in the "neurophysiological" system that exists in the human

organism because it involves changes in human energy (even though the motivation arises from within humans), its appearance will involve human physical activities. b. Motivation is characterized by the appearance, feeling, or "feeling", of one's affection. In this case, motivation is relevant to psychological, affective, and energy issues that can determine human behavior. c. Motivation will be stimulated because of the purpose. So motivation in this case is a response to an action, namely a goal. Motivation does arise from within humans, but its emergence is due to being stimulated or driven by the presence of other elements, in this case, the goal. This goal will be related to needs.

According to George and Jones (in Sakiman, 2019: 36) suggest 3 aspects of work motivation, including a. Behavior (direction of behavior), b. Level of effort, c. Level of Persistence. Winardi (in Sakiman, 2019: 36) reveals that there are three aspects of motivation that lead to the achievement of certain goals, namely a. Desire, when someone has a desire, his motivation is spurred to do a job to achieve what he wants. b. Needs, someone has high motivation when someone needs. When someone needs something such as salary, compensation, the work will be motivated to do a good job, c. A sense of security, someone will try to do something is also due to fear when the person does not do something so the motivational reason arises because when someone does something he feels safe. According to Sakiman, (2019: 36) aspects of work motivation are: a. Discipline, b. High imagination and combination power, c. Confidence, d. Pressure resistance, e. Responsibilities in doing work, f. Behavior (direction of behavior), g. Level of effort, h. Level of persistence, i. Desire, j. Needs, k. Sense of security.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the motivational aspects are the level of effort, resistance to pressure, persistence, focus on goals.

➤ *Self Efficacy*

According to Rivai & Esas (2021: 74) Self-efficacy is a person's belief that he can carry out a task at a certain level. Furthermore, Bandura (in Prasetyawan, 2018: 275-276) explains that self-efficacy is the belief in an individual's ability to organize and take the necessary actions to achieve certain goals. This self-confidence becomes the foundation or basis for an individual to act. An individual tends to perform a task or activity that they feel confident about having competence, but avoids the opposite. Self-efficacy is a determinant of the resilience and persistence of an individual in facing difficulties and how much effort they make to resolve these difficulties. An individual with high self-efficacy has expectations of success and always persists in carrying out activities to completion.

According to Muhadjir (in Suhesty et al, 2021: 191), self-efficacy or self-efficacy is self-confidence that he has the ability to organize and carry out the necessary work steps, is able to take initiative steps, is able to overcome obstacles and to finally produce something good. It needs to be achieved.

According to Raudhoh & Karmila (2021: 38) self-efficacy is an individual's optimistic attitude in solving any problems that occur with full persistence and a sense of responsibility in order to get results as expected with indicators of confidence to overcome difficulties, ability to complete tasks, persistence in completing tasks, self-evaluation ability.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that self-efficacy is a belief or expectation of one's ability or competence to perform a task, achieve goals and overcome obstacles well.

➤ *Aspects of Self-Efficacy*

A person's self-efficacy can be increased through the four aspects of Bandura's sources (in Faadhil et al., 2020: 135), the first source is personal success experience (enactive mastery experience), personal success experiences provide authentic evidence to a person about what he can do to succeed at a particular task, so that personal experience is the source that most influences a person's self-efficacy. The second source is the experience of others (vicarious experience), the experience of others can be a source of efficacy through the modeling process or imitating the experiences of other people's success. The thing that needs to be considered in this process is the equality of a person's capacity with the model to be imitated, the more equal a person's condition is with the model's condition, the more it affects a person's self-efficacy. The third source of verbal persuasion, the source of efficacy through verbal persuasion is done by convincing someone that he can do certain tasks, someone who is successfully convinced will try more and be more persistent in the face of difficulties or challenges. The fourth source is physiological and affective states, physiological conditions such as endurance, health, and limb function affects a person's self-efficacy to perform certain tasks, as well as emotional conditions such as happiness, sadness, and fear as well. affect a person's self-efficacy to perform certain tasks.

Bandura (in Ediaty & Wohon, 2019: 66) aspects of self-efficacy include; the first aspect is the level or the degree to which a person's belief in his or her ability to solve a problem or task with different levels of problem difficulty according to their abilities, the second aspect is a generality, which focuses on one's belief in a given task and one's belief in assessing a task according to his ability, and the last aspect, namely Strength leads to the belief in the endurance and persistence of the individual in carrying out his duties. So that it can be seen how individuals have confidence that they can take advantage of their abilities according to the circumstances to be able to complete the given task smoothly.

Baron (in Raudhoh & Karmila (2021: 37-38) states that there are three aspects of self-efficacy, including a) Academic self-efficacy relates to students' beliefs about the ability to perform tasks, manage learning activities and live with individual academic expectations. themselves and others b. Social self-efficacy relates to the individual's belief in his

ability to form and maintain relationships, assertiveness, and perform activities in his spare time c. Self-regulatory self-efficacy relates to the ability to resist peer pressure and prevent high-risk activities.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the aspects of self-efficacy are belief in one's ability, focus on the task, never give up and keep the spirit.

➤ *Factors that affect self-efficacy*

Tentaman & Mukti (2019: 346) concluded that the factors that influence self-efficacy are not only influenced by factors from within the individual (internal) but can also be influenced by external factors (external). Internal factors that affect academic self-efficacy, namely: interest, patience, resilience, character, motivation. Meanwhile, external factors that affect self-efficacy are attachment style, warmth, goal orientation, enactive mastery experiences, and verbal persuasion.

According to Jess & Gregory (in Almadana & Santoso, 2021: 21) say four factors influence being an important source of self-efficacy, including a. Experience of past performance; b. Unexpected experiences from other people; c. Social persuasion; d. Psychological and emotional conditions. Self-efficacy becomes a self-confidence to know one's ability so that it can exercise a form of control over the individual's benefits and events in the surrounding environment.

According to Ndjaua et al (2018: 137-138), many factors influence self-efficacy, one of which is family support and motivation. Individuals with high family support can increase higher motivation. Self-efficacy helps a person in making choices, efforts to move forward, as well as persistence and perseverance in maintaining the tasks that cover their lives. Self-efficacy affects how a person thinks, feels, motivates himself, and acts and uses time or control over time.

Another opinion is explained by Raudhoh & Karmila (2021: 38) that the factors that influence self-efficacy are: a. Behavioral selection is a very important factor as a source of formation of student self-efficacy because it is based on the fact that the success of students in carrying out a particular task or skill will increase self-efficacy and repeated failures will reduce self-efficacy.

- The amount of effort and perseverance that is a strong belief about the effectiveness of students' abilities will greatly determine the effort to try to overcome difficult situations. Efficacy considerations also determine how much effort will be made and how long it will last in the face of challenges. The stronger the self-efficacy, the longer it will last in the business.
- The way of thinking and emotional reactions is that in solving difficult problems, students who have high efficacy tend to attribute failure to fewer efforts, while

students who have low efficacy consider failure to come from the lack of student abilities.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that the factors that influence self-efficacy are motivational effort, thought patterns, resistance to stress, control over time (time management), and success and failure in larger groups.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The method in this study uses quantitatively by using an incidental sampling technique.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aims to see the effect of timemanagement and motivation on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their

thesis while working. Determination of the research scene was carried out after making observations in several hotels in the city of Semarang. The following is an explanation of the initial list of the names of the hotels where the research is conducted and the number of subjects, as follows: Hotel subject LP 5, subject Hotel LS 5, subject Hotel LPN 20, subject Hotel CP 2, subject Hotel AP 2, subject Hotel C2, Hotel SP2 subject. Hotel DH 2 subjects, Hotel GC 1 subject, Hotel GT 1 subject, Hotel CA 1 subject, Hotel IS 1 subject, Hotel N 1 subject, Hotel PH 1 subject, Hotel QH 1 subject, Hotel TC 1 subject, Hotel TH 1 subject, Hotel NM 1 subject. The total number of subjects in this study was 50 subjects. The considerations made by researchers researching several hotels in the city of Semarang are as follows: There is a problem that needs to be done, namely the lack of time management and motivation for procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working.

➤ *Auter loading final model*

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

➤ *Construct Validity and Reliability Test*

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Reliability composite	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Self efficacy	0.973	0.975	0.975	0.630
Time management	0.964	0.965	0.967	0.593
Motivation	0.976	0.978	0.978	0.637
Procrastination	0.974	0.976	0.976	0.638

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

Based on the above, it shows that the research variables have composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha values above 0.70. Therefore, the indicators used in this research variable are said to be reliable. Meanwhile, to test the validity of using the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value with a limit value above 0.50. For variables that have an AVE value above 0.50, it can be interpreted that all items and variables are declared valid.

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

	Self efficacy	Time management	Motivation	Procrastination
Self efficacy	0.794			
Time management	0.633	0.770		
Motivation	0.603	0.451	0.798	
Procrastination	0.843	0.718	0.690	0.799

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

In the table above, the comparison of the AVE root values shows that each of these values is greater than the correlation between other variables, so it can be concluded that all latent variables in the study have good discriminant validity.

➤ *R-Square*

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

Based on the above, it is known that the R-Square value for the self-efficacy variable is 0.528 which can be interpreted that

the magnitude of the influence of time management and motivation variables on procrastination through self-efficacy is 52.8% while the remaining 47.2% is explained by other variables outside of this study. The R-Square value for the procrastination variable is 0.808, which means that 80.8% of the procrastination variable is influenced by time management, motivation and self-efficacy, while the remaining 19.2% is influenced by variables outside this study.

➤ *Path Coefficient*

	Sampel Original (O)	Average Sampel (M)	Standar Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values
Self efficacy-> Procrastination	0.514	0.505	0.149	3.444	0.001
Time management ->Self efficacy	0.453	0.460	0.156	2.906	0.004
Time management ->Procrastination	0.278	0.290	0.112	2.492	0.013
Motivation -> Self efficacy	0.399	0.403	0.172	2.324	0.021
Motivation -> Procrastination	0.254	0.254	0.153	1.664	0.097

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

The first hypothesis is that self-efficacy on procrastination has a significant negative effect, this can be seen from the t statistic value of 3.444 and the p-value of 0.001 < 0.05. The original sample value is 0.514 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between self-efficacy and procrastination is negative. Thus the first hypothesis is accepted.

The second hypothesis is that time management on self-efficacy has a significant positive effect, this can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.906 and p-value of 0.004 < 0.05. The original sample value is 0.453 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between time management and self-efficacy is positive. Thus the second hypothesis is accepted.

The third hypothesis is that time management on procrastination has a significant negative effect, this can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.492 and p-value of 0.013 < 0.05. The original sample value is 0.278 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between time management and procrastination is negative. Thus the third hypothesis is accepted.

The fourth hypothesis is that motivation on self- efficacy has a significant effect in a positive direction, this can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.324 and p-value of 0.021 < 0.05.

The original sample value is 0.399 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between motivation and self- efficacy is positive. Thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

The fifth hypothesis is that motivation on procrastination has no significant effect, this can be seen from the t statistics value of 1.664 and p-value of 0.097 < 0.05. The original sample value is 0.254 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between motivation and procrastination has no effect. Thus the fifth hypothesis is rejected.

➤ *Specific Indirect Effect*

	Sampel Original (O)	Average Sampel (M)	Standar Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Time management -> Self efficacy -> Procrastination	0.233	0.234	0.109	2.145	0.032
Motivation -> Self efficacy -> Procrastination	0.205	0.198	0.100	2.040	0.042

Source: Research result, processed with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021.

The sixth hypothesis is that the indirect effect of time management on procrastination through self- efficacy has a significant value of t statistics of 2.145 > 1.66 and a p-value of 0.032 < 0.05.

While the seventh hypothesis, namely the influence of motivation on procrastination through self- efficacy, has a significant value of t statistics of 2,040 > 1.66 and a p-value of 0.042 < 0.05. From the above test, it appears that the mediator in the model shows that time management and motivation partially have a significant influence on procrastination through self- efficacy.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *Effect of Time Management on Procrastination.*

From the examination of research results, there is a significant effect between time management on procrastination in a negative direction. This is by the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.278 which shows the t statistics value of 2.492 > 1.66 and the p-value of 0.013 < 0.05. So it can be said that the time management variable has a significant effect on the procrastination variable. It can be interpreted that the higher the time management, the lower the procrastination, and vice versa. Good time management is one of the important factors that can determine success both in career and in college assignments. Time management is concerned with how someone can organize or schedule each of his activities so that all work can be completed properly and on time. Things like this are often overlooked, even though implementing a good time management system can increase the chances of success being developed. Conceptually, time management problems can affect individuals in procrastinating, poor time management can be a factor in procrastination

behavior.

In line with Pertiwi's opinion (2020: 745) explains that there is a significant negative effect between time management and procrastination, individuals who experience procrastination are not because they don't want to know the work or task they are facing. However, it's just that the individual diverts his mind and attention so that it delays the time to do it which causes failure to complete the task on time.

Another opinion that is in line with the above research is the previous research proposed by Mamahit & Setiawan (2020: 133) that the ability to manage time or time management has a significant negative effect on procrastination, this is explained by the higher ability to manage time or time management, the lower procrastination.

➤ *The effect of motivation on procrastination*

The effect of motivation on procrastination has no significant effect, this is by the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.254, it can be seen from the t statistics value of 1.664 > 1.66 and the p-value of 0.097 < 0.05. From this research, it is known that there is no influence of motivation on procrastination, in other words, individuals still have motivation even though they delay the work or task they are doing. In contrast to the opinion of Marwan and Stevani (2021: 129) motivation has a negative effect on procrastination, meaning that the higher the motivation, the lower the procrastination, as well as previous research conducted by Mardi et al (2021: 31) there is a negative influence between motivation on procrastination in students, meaning that if the motivation to achieve a task or job has increased at one point, procrastination will decrease.

But in this study based on the results of data analysis obtained that there is no significant relationship between motivation and procrastination in Masters or Masters level students who work while studying. Individual motivation has no effect in reducing or increasing procrastination behavior in Masters or Masters level students. Further research needs to examine other factors that influence procrastination in Masters or Masters level students, both from within the individual and factors outside the individual.

➤ *Effect of self-efficacy on procrastination*

Self-efficacy on procrastination has a significant negative effect, this is by the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.514 and can be seen from the t statistics value of 3.444 > 1.66 and p-value of 0.001 < 0.05. This study is in line with Handoyo et al (2021: 42) research conducted on student subjects with the results showing that self-efficacy influences procrastination. The relationship between self-efficacy and procrastination has a negative relationship direction. That is, if students' self-efficacy is high, it can reduce procrastination behavior, and vice versa.

Other research that is in line with the theoretical opinion above is according to Dewi & Erdianto (2020: 39) the results of research that have been carried out show that there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and procrastination. The significant relationship between the two variables also shows a negative value, meaning that between self-efficacy and procrastination there is a non-unidirectional relationship. The lower the self-efficacy, the higher the procrastination that is raised, and vice versa.

➤ *The effect of time management on self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working.*

Time management on self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who work on their thesis while working, has a significant positive effect, this is in accordance with the results of path coefficients with an original sample value of 0.453 and can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.906 > 1.66 and p-value are 0.004 < 0.05. The method of time management or time management involves the individual's self-confidence to manage any work or task. According to Alsa & Conscience (2021: 59), specifically effective time management can increase self-efficacy. The higher the time management, the higher the self-efficacy, and vice versa.

Other research that agrees with the above research is according to Amran et al (2021:149-154) in their research that the better individuals manage time, the better self-efficacy for setting goals, using active learning strategies, evaluating progress on goals, and creating an effective environment for doing work. or task. This means that the higher the time setting, the self-efficacy will also increase, and vice versa.

➤ *The effect of motivation on self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working.*

Motivation towards self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students working on a thesis while working is significant in a positive direction, this is in accordance with the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.399 and can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.324 > 1.66 and the p-value of 0.021 < 0.05. In line with the research by Setiyaningsih & Nurmalia (2020: 50), there is a positive direct influence of motivation on self-efficacy. Motivation is very influential both on self-efficacy or it can be said that increasing motivation will increase self-efficacy, the higher the motivation, the higher the self-efficacy.

Another opinion that is in line with the results of the research above is Jati et al (2020: 21) motivational variables have a very positive effect on self-efficacy, this shows that the higher student motivation, self-efficacy will also increase, and vice versa.

➤ *The effect of time management on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable.*

There is a positive and significant effect between time management through self-efficacy and a negative effect on procrastination as a dependent variable. This is in accordance with the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.233 and can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.145 > 1.66 and the p-value of 0.032 < 0.05. So it can be said that the time management variable has a positive and significant effect through the self-efficacy variable as an intervening variable and has a negative effect on the dependent variable procrastination. The higher the time management, the higher the self-efficacy and will reduce the level of procrastination.

➤ *The effect of motivation on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable.*

There is a positive and significant influence between motivation through self-efficacy as an intervening variable and a negative influence on the procrastination variable. This is in accordance with the results of path coefficients with the original sample value of 0.205 and can be seen from the t statistics value of 2.040 > 1.66 and the p-value of 0.042 < 0.05. So it can be said that the motivation variable has a positive and significant effect through the self-efficacy variable as an intervening variable and has a negative effect on the dependent variable procrastination. The higher the motivation, the higher the self-efficacy and the lower the level of procrastination.

➤ *Is there an effect of time management and motivation on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working.*

There is a significant negative effect between time management on procrastination, it can be concluded that when time management is good, procrastination will decrease, and vice versa. Then the influence of motivation has no significant effect on procrastination, individual motivation has no effect on reducing or increasing procrastination behavior in Masters or Masters level students. Further research needs to examine other factors. Self-efficacy on procrastination has a significant negative effect, meaning that the higher the self-efficacy, the lower the procrastination behavior.

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that there is a significant negative effect between time management on procrastination, it can be concluded that when time management is good, procrastination will decrease, and vice versa. Then the influence of motivation has no significant effect on procrastination, individual motivation has no effect on reducing or increasing procrastination behavior in Masters or Masters level students. Further research needs to examine other factors. Self-efficacy on procrastination has a significant negative effect, meaning that the higher the self-efficacy, the lower the procrastination behavior.

SUGGESTION

- For other researchers. For other researchers who are interested in continuing this research, it is hoped that they will be able to see the factors that influence time management and motivation on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working. Other researchers are advised to pay attention to the sampling technique and item arrangement technique used so as to avoid errors in the distribution of the scale on the subject.
- For academics. a. The research is only conducted on employee X with the criteria of students who are in Masters or Masters courses who are working. Therefore, further research is carried out with a different paradigm and has more respondents. b. The research carried out only uses the data analysis method with SmartPLS 3.0, 2021. Therefore, further research is recommended to use other analytical methods such as LISREL, AMOS, and soon. c. This research only examines the effect of time management and motivation variables on procrastination with self-efficacy as an intervening variable in master's degree students who do their thesis while working. Therefore, further research examines other variables that affect procrastination.

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